

PROTOCOL FOR SAMPLE PREPARATION OF ORGANIC COMPOUNDS IN THE PARTICULATE AND GASEOUS PHASES OF AMBIENT AIR PRIOR TO GC-MS ANALYSIS

Célia Alves

Department of Environment and Planning, Centre for Environmental and Marine Studies, University of Aveiro, 3810-193 Aveiro, Portugal

1. Introduction/Scope

Organic compounds constitute a substantial fraction of atmospheric particulate matter (PM) and play a critical role in determining its chemical composition, emission sources, atmospheric transformations, and associated environmental and health impacts. In atmospheric aerosols, they include a chemically diverse range of species, such as primary compounds directly emitted from combustion and non-combustion sources, including polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), n-alkanes, and hopanes, as well as oxidation products formed in the atmosphere that contribute to secondary organic aerosol (SOA) formation. Many organic compounds are semi-volatile and dynamically partition between the gas and particulate phases as a function of temperature, relative humidity, aerosol composition, and particulate mass concentration. This multiphase behaviour complicates both their accurate quantification and the interpretation of their atmospheric fate, source contributions, and implications in air quality studies.

This document describes an extraction method for the determination of organic compounds by gas chromatography–mass spectrometry (GC–MS) from samples collected using high-volume samplers that simultaneously collect PM on filters and the gaseous phase on polyurethane foam (PUF).

2. Methodology

Atmospheric particulate matter and semi-volatile organic compounds are commonly sampled using high-volume air samplers equipped with filters for particle collection and PUF plugs for the gaseous phase. Organic species are subsequently recovered from filters and PUFs through solvent extraction procedures, followed by fractionation using flash chromatography. Selected compound classes, particularly those containing hydroxyl or carboxylic functional groups, undergo derivatisation prior to instrumental analysis to improve their volatility and

chromatographic performance. The identification and quantification of the target organic compounds are then carried out by GC–MS.

3. Reagents

3.1. Acetone

3.2. Dichloromethane (DCM)

3.3. Methanol (Met)

3.4. Hexane

3.5. Toluene

3.6. Ethyl acetate

3.7. Formic acid

3.8. BSTFA-TMCS (N,O-bis (trimethylsilyl) trifluoroacetamide with 1% of TMS)

3.9. Diazald

3.10. Ethyl ether

3.11. Acetic acid

3.12. Potassium dichromate

3.13. Sulphuric acid

3.14 Silica gel 60 Å and 230-400 mesh, suitable for low pressure liquid chromatography.

Note: The type of silica and its treatment should be kept as consistent as possible among all users; otherwise, variations in separation properties may lead to differences in fractionation behaviour and subsequent analytical inconsistencies.

4. Materials and treatment

4.0. Preparation of chrome-sulphuric solution ($K_2Cr_2O_7 + H_2SO_4$ concentrated) for glass pipette cleaning: dissolve 5 – 6 g of potassium dichromate in 100 ml of distilled water and add carefully and slowly 100 ml of concentrated sulphuric acid.

Attention: *Be careful with this solution because it is very corrosive. USE GLOVES, LABORATORY COAT AND SAFETY GLASSES AND PERFORM THE OPERATION IN A FUME HOOD. If solution drops on the skin, wash immediately with abundant water and then with a solution of sodium hydrogen carbonate. Apart from being corrosive, the most important feature is its high toxicity due to Cr(VI).*

Note: This solution may be used several times until showing a greenish colour.

4.1. Clean up of disposable Pasteur pipettes (glass)

4.1.1. Fill a tall glass container with Pasteur pipettes and add chrome-sulphuric solution. Cover and leave in this solution overnight.

4.1.2. Remove the chrome-sulphuric solution and wash the pipettes with distilled water.

4.1.3. Wash the pipettes in ultra pure water in an ultrasonic bath for 15 minutes. Repeat the ultrasonic treatment once again.

4.1.4. Heat the pipettes 4 hours at 300°C in an oven (leave the pipettes inside the glass Goblet, covered with aluminium foil).

4.2. Clean up of pipette bulbs (natural rubber) used with Pasteur pipettes

4.2.1. Heat in an oven at 30°C for 24 hours. This is particularly important to reduce contamination with phthalates. Since phthalates are not volatile enough to be completely removed at this temperature, this treatment is only effective if solvents never get in contact with the bulbs during extraction and sample treatment.

4.3. Clean up of vials

4.3.1. Fill each vial with acetone and immerse in a glass with the same solvent. Take the glass to the ultrasonic bath for 15 minutes.

4.3.2. Throw out the acetone and wash with ultra-pure water.

4.3.3. Fill each vial with ultra-pure water, immerse in a glass with ultra-pure water and take the glass to ultrasonic bath for 15 minutes.

4.3.4. Remove the water and dry at 100°C in an oven (at least 1 h).

4.3.5. Wrap each vial with aluminium foil and bake at 500°C for 6 hours.

4.3.6. Transfer the wrapped vials to a clean container.

4.4. Clean up of tweezers, spatulas (lab spoons) and scalpels

4.4.1. Introduce the objects into a test tube and fill with methanol. Cover the test tube with aluminium foil and sonicate for 15 minutes.

4.4.2. Repeat sonication (15 mins) with dichloromethane.

4.4.3. Keep the objects in the test tube, let it dry and store in a clean container.

4.5. Clean up of flash chromatographic column stopcock and screw cap vials

4.5.1. Put the taps and caps into a glass and fill with methanol. Cover the glass with aluminium foil and sonicate for 15 minutes.

4.5.2. Repeat sonication (15 mins) with dichloromethane.

4.5.3. Transfer taps and caps to a clean container and allow them to dry.

4.6. Clean up of re-usable glassware (for which oven baking is necessary)

This section covers the cleaning of the following items (others used in a specific laboratory may require similar treatment):

- Pear-shaped flasks
- Open-column chromatographic columns
- Kilner jars (for storage of PUF cylinders)
- Funnels
- Round-bottom flasks (500 ml)
- Erlenmeyer (stoppered) flasks
- Soxhlets
- Weighing boxes with caps
- Beakers (Measuring cylinders)
- Stirring rods
- Rotary evaporator adapters

4.6.1. As soon as possible after use, rinse the glassware with the last solvent used in it, followed by high-purity acetone and finally with hexane.

4.6.2. Wash the material with detergent and tap water.

4.6.3. Rinse several times with distilled water.

4.6.4. Dry the glassware at 100°C for 1 hour.

4.6.5. Wrap glassware with aluminium foil and heat at 500°C for 6 hours.

4.7. Clean up of glassware (for which oven baking is not possible)

This section covers the cleaning of the following items:

- Volumetric flasks
- Petri dishes
- Solvent bottles
- Allihn condensers

- 4.7.1.** Immerse glassware into a chrome sulphuric solution (several hours/overnight).
- 4.7.2.** Rinse the material several times with distilled water.
- 4.7.3.** Dry the glassware at 100°C for one hour, except for volumetric flasks that should dry at ambient temperature.

Note: Before utilization, the glassware must be rinsed with the solvent to be used.

4.8. Cleaning of Rotary Evaporator (RE)

4.8.1. The RE should be rinsed with acetone when evaporating samples with different concentrations and/or chemical compositions to avoid cross-contamination. For this purpose, add approximately 250 mL of acetone to a round-bottom flask, connect it to the RE, and evaporate the solvent completely under normal operating conditions.

4.8.2. For the same sample use the same adaptor. Between the evaporation of each one of the organic fractions (aliphatic, PAH, aldehydes/ketones, alcohols/esters and fatty acids), rinse the RE adaptor with acetone and dichloromethane.

4.8.3. For a different sample use a fresh clean adaptor.

Note: The RE bath is filled with bidistilled water.

4.9. Nitrogen atmosphere for dryness

4.9.1. For each vial, use a clean Pasteur pipette in the evaporative apparatus under a dry nitrogen atmosphere.

4.10. Clean up of cotton wool and silica

To minimise contamination, all materials used in the sample extraction are pre-extracted in a Soxhlet apparatus.

4.10.1. Purify the material using a series of 3 consecutive extractions in a Soxhlet apparatus (24 hours extraction for each solvent):

- First extraction: 300 ml of a methanol + acetone (50:50) mixture
- Second extraction: 300 ml of dichloromethane
- Third extraction: 300 ml of dichloromethane

Note: Before introducing for the first time the material in the Soxhlet apparatus, perform an extraction for 4 hours of the cellulose extraction thimbles with 300 ml of a methanol + acetone (50:50) mixture. Discard solvents.

4.10.1.1. Cotton wool purification

4.10.1.1.1. Place the cotton wool inside the sorbent cartridges and add 300 ml of the mixture methanol + acetone to the flat-bottom flask. Connect all Soxhlet parts and extract for 24 hours.

4.10.1.1.2. Disconnect, remove the solvent, and add 300 ml of dichloromethane. Perform the extraction for 24 h.

4.10.1.1.3. Repeat as above.

4.10.1.1.4. Remove the cotton wool from the cartridge and store in a clean sealed glass container.

Note: The used thimbles, after solvent evaporation in a fume hood, are placed in a flask covered with aluminium foil. Dry for 3 hours at 30-40°C in an oven.

4.10.1.2. Silica purification

4.10.1.2.1. Fill the sorbent cartridges with silica and cover with a thin layer of cotton wool (to avoid material suspension). Follow the same procedure used for cotton wool purification.

4.11. Treatment of filters and PUFs

4.11.1.1. If the filters are to be cut in the laboratory rather than purchased pre-cut, cut the filters to the correct shapes over a glass plate previously rinsed with DCM, using a metallic plate (with the cut filter shape) and a scalpel also rinsed with DCM.

4.11.1.2. Place the filters (whether cut in the laboratory or purchased pre-cut) inside aluminium foil not completely closed.

4.11.1.3. Transfer the filters to a muffle furnace, and heat to 500°C for 6 hours.

4.11.1.4. Transfer the filters to a desiccator in the presence of silica-gel and allow to cool.

4.11.1.5. Wrap the filters in the same aluminium foil used in the muffle furnace. Label the aluminium foil and store in a clean container prior to sampling.

4.11.3. PUF cylinders

4.11.3.1 PUF cylinders (dimensions 13 cm height x 9 cm diameter in total for each sample – this may be made up of 2-4 smaller cylinders of 9 cm diameter, as long as the total PUF volume per sample is maintained) are pre-extracted prior to use. Pre-extraction may be

conducted using either a soxhlet apparatus or an Accelerated Solvent Extraction (ASE) device.

4.11.3.2 PUF cylinders may be re-used. The presence of chemical additives such as flame-retardants and plasticisers in the "raw" PUF means that before their 1st use, the pre-extraction must be more rigorous than for subsequent uses.

4.11.3.3 Prior to 1st use, introduce the PUF cylinder(s) into the extraction apparatus. Extract with an appropriate volume of DCM for 8 h, discard the solvent and repeat. This should normally suffice, but - as additive levels in PUF can vary widely - it is recommended that a "PUF-blank" analysis be conducted prior to full-scale use. If analyte concentrations in this blank are of concern and exceed those in a corresponding "reagent blank" (i.e. an analysis conducted without sample or clean pre-extracted PUF), then incorporate an additional 8 h pre-extraction with DCM to the pre-extraction protocol.

4.11.3.4 After the 1st use, PUFs must be pre-extracted via soxhlet or ASE with one volume of DCM for 8 h prior to subsequent use.

4.11.3.5 After pre-extraction, lay PUFs on clean aluminium foil and allow solvent to evaporate in a clean fume hood for 4 h, before wrapping in the foil and storing at room temperature in a clean, sealed Kilner jar. **Note:** If more than one PUF cylinder is used for a given sample, all cylinders may be stored in the same Kilner jar, provided that the jar dimensions allow adequate accommodation without compressing the material.

5. Sampling and samples

5.1. Sampler configuration

PM2.5 = Backup filter + PUF cartridge
PM10 = Impactor + Backup filter + PUF cartridge

Figure 1. Schematic representation of a high-volume sampler

Figure 1 shows a high-volume sampler configuration equipped with an impaction plate that enables the simultaneous collection of coarse particulate matter (PM_{2.5-10}) and fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}), followed by the retention of volatile and semi-volatile compounds in the PUF cartridge. The flow rate should be regulated by a flow controller connected to a pump and set at 1.113 L/min.

5.2. Clean up of the sampling system

5.2.1. Between each sampling, clean the aluminium impaction plates with a brush and, if necessary, with acetone, to remove any residues from the impactor slots.

5.2.2. When dirt accumulates (once per week, for example), the net and the inside of the high volume PM₁₀ inlet head should be cleaned with a cloth and distilled water.

5.3. High volume sampler calibration

Calibrate the high-volume sampler in the field using a calibrated flow rate orifice, whenever necessary (before each campaign and after major repairs or maintenance).

Note: See the standard procedure provided by the manufacturer.

5.4 Addition of Sampling Evaluation Standard

Immediately before transporting the pre-cleaned PUF cylinders from the laboratory to the sampling site, spike the PUF with an appropriate amount of a sampling evaluation standard (SES). The standard should be injected at the air-entry side of the PUF cylinder (i.e., the end closest to the impactor). When more than one PUF cylinder is used per sample, only the cylinder positioned nearest to the impactor should be spiked. After SES addition, return the PUF cylinder to the Kilner jar and seal it prior to transport to the sampling site.

By default, PCB congener #147 is used as the SES at a loading of 20 ng per sample (e.g., 20 µL of a 1 ng µL⁻¹ solution). Alternative SES compounds may also be employed, provided they satisfy the following criteria: resistance to degradation under sampling conditions, suitability for GC-MS analysis without derivatisation, and a vapour pressure within the range of the target analytes.

5.5. Filter treatment after sampling

5.5.1. After sampling, filters are folded, exposed face against exposed face, and wrapped with the previously used aluminium foil. They are placed inside sealable plastic bags (to

prevent water/humidity being directly in contact with filters) and stored as soon as possible in a freezer (-18°C) until transport to the laboratory (do not forget to label the external aluminium surface).

5.6. PUF cylinder treatment after sampling

After sampling, PUF cylinders are wrapped in the previously used aluminium foil, placed into their Kilner jars and stored as soon as possible in a freezer (-18°C) until transport to the laboratory.

6. Analytical Technique

6.1. Sample Extraction

6.1.1. Place the filter or PUF cylinder to be extracted into the extraction apparatus, taking care to ensure that the sample identification details are recorded.

6.1.2. Treat each sample (i.e., PM_{2.5-10} filter or PUF cylinder(s) and PM_{2.5} filter combined with an appropriate amount of internal standards. The ideal amount will depend on the anticipated concentrations of the target analytes at the sampling location, but as a default will be 20 ng of each (e.g. 20 µl of a 1 ng µl⁻¹ solution).

6.1.3. The internal standards to be used for fractions 1 (aliphatics) and 2 (aromatics) are a range of isotopically-labelled (typically deuterated) PAH and n-alkanes. For fraction 3 (aldehydes and ketones) use 13C6-diethylhexylphthalate. For fraction 4 (esters), deuterated 2,4,5-trichlorophenol will be employed. For fraction 5 (sugars and acids), C18 deuterated carboxylic acid (Stearic-d35 acid) will be added.

6.1.4. Perform the extraction with an appropriate volume of DCM for an suitable time. For soxhlet extraction, the recommended volume is 300 ml for 24 h; for ASE the recommended volume is 50 ml for 15 min.

6.1.5. After extraction, allow the crude extract to cool to ambient temperature. Rinse the extraction apparatus with three x 20 ml aliquots of DCM and combine with the crude extract. Cover the crude extract container with aluminium foil and continue with the next operation - filtration and concentration.

6.2. Filtration

Place the pre-extracted cotton wool in a funnel and filter the crude extract into a round-bottomed flask. Rinse the crude extract container to the filter with DCM.

6.3. Evaporation/concentration – Rotary evaporator

6.3.1. Set the RE bath thermostat control temperature to 33°C.

6.3.2. Ensure water flow through the condenser.

6.3.3. Wash the RE adaptor first with acetone and then with DCM.

6.3.4. Connect the round-bottomed flask containing the crude sample extract to the RE (see point 4.8.).

6.3.5. Turn off the stopcock to obtain vacuum and turn on the pump.

6.3.6. Turn on the RE, and carefully evaporate solvent to a volume of 2-4 ml.

6.3.7. Transfer the concentrate to a pre-cleaned glass vial, ensuring that it is securely labelled with the sample identification details.

6.3.8. Dry the vial extract with a nitrogen flow (Fig. 2).

6.3.9. The extracts are stored at 4°C or at -18°C if the fractionation procedure is not applied in the same or in the next day.

Figure 2. Laboratory setup used for the fractionation of organic compounds from the sample and for the evaporation/drying of the different organic extracts.

(A) Needle valves

(B) N50 nitrogen cylinder

(C) Nitrogen blowdown evaporator

(D) Vials containing the organic extracts from the different fractions

(E) Silica gel column for sample fractionation

6.4. Preparation of chromatographic column for fractionation

6.4.1. Weigh accurately 1.5 g of silica into a glass weighing bottle and activate for 3 hours at 150°C. Cool it in a desiccator. As the silica gel characteristics are crucial for the reproducibility of the fractionation process, we cannot store activated silica gel for a long period. A wise period should be like a week (maximum) as soon as the storing conditions were completely fulfilled.

6.4.2. Insert a stopcock at the end of the column and a pressure flow adapter at the top that is linked to the nitrogen supply via a Teflon tube. Using tweezers and a glass rod of appropriate length, place a small portion of cotton wool inside the column and press down in order to obtain a compacted surface.

6.4.3. Add hexane to the silica gel in the weighing box and transfer carefully to the column. Repeat this step until all the silica gel is transferred.

6.5. Fractionation process - preparation

6.5.1. Have 4 crimp cap vials and 1 screw cap vials pre-cleaned and identify each one with a label:

- 1 Capsulate vial - 1st fraction (aliphatics)
- 1 Capsulate vial – 2nd fraction (PAHs)
- 1 Capsulate vial – 3rd fraction (aldehydes and ketones)
- 1 Capsulate vial – 4th fraction (alcohols and esters)
- 1 Screw vial – 5th fraction (fatty acids and sugars)

6.5.2. Add to the vial 1 mL of hexane. Seal the vial and store at 4 °C until fractionation.

Note: storage time prior to fractionation should be minimised.

6.6. Flash Chromatography

6.6.1. Prepare five stoppered (Erlenmeyer) flasks with the following solvents:

1. 15 ml hexane (aliphatic fraction)
2. 9.6 ml hexane + 5.4 ml toluene (PAH fraction)
3. 7.5 ml hexane + 7.5 DCM (aldehydes and ketones fraction)
4. 12 ml hexane + 8 ml ethyl acetate (alcohol and esters fraction)

5. 30 ml of formic acid in methanol-4% (in a volumetric flask of 500 ml, add 20 ml of formic acid and complete the volume with methanol) (fatty acids and sugars fraction)

6.6.2. Assemble four x 25 ml pear-shape flasks (first four fractions) and one x 50 ml (last fraction).

6.6.3. Place a 25 ml pear-shape flask under the column exit to collect the eluate. With a Pasteur pipette transfer the contents of the vial containing the portion of the crude sample extract for fractionation to the top of the chromatographic column. Repeat this process rinsing the vial with three portions of hexane taken from the 15 ml hexane contained in the stoppered flask

6.6.4. Open the stopcock to allow the solvent and crude extract to flow into the silica column bed. Once the entire extract and solvent have entered the column, close the stopcock, ensuring that the surface of the silica bed does not run dry.

6.6.5. With the stopcock closed, carefully add the remaining ~12 mL of hexane from the stoppered flask, taking care not to disturb the surface of the silica bed.

6.6.6. Connect the column to the nitrogen supply, but do not initiate the nitrogen flow at this stage. Open the column stopcock and then start the nitrogen flow. Allow the solvent to elute at a constant flow rate of approximately 1.2 mL min^{-1} (equivalent to about 1 drop s^{-1}), ensuring that the surface of the silica bed does not run dry. Maintaining this flow rate consistently is critical for reproducible fractionation.

6.6.7. Once all the solvent has eluted through the column, switch off the nitrogen supply, close the stopcock, remove the pear-shaped flask containing the eluate and stop it up until ready for solvent evaporation.

6.6.8. For the subsequent fractions, carefully add the appropriate solvent, taking care not to disturb the surface of the silica bed, and then follow steps 6.6.6 and 6.6.7. As described in Section 6.3.3, use a portion of the solvent to rinse the vial to ensure complete transfer of the sample.

6.6.9. For fractions 2 and 3, add a small amount of methanol (~2 ml) to the pear-shape flask containing the column eluate prior to solvent evaporation (to facilitate evaporation).

6.6.10. Using a RE apparatus, evaporate carefully the solvent in each pear-shaped flask to dryness.

6.6.11. Using a Pasteur pipette, transfer the contents of each pear-shaped flask to separate 1 mL vials, rinsing the flask with dichloromethane (DCM) to ensure quantitative transfer. Carefully evaporate the solvent under a gentle nitrogen stream to near dryness. Store the extracts in a freezer at $-18 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ until analysis or shipment to another laboratory.

6.6.12. Immediately prior to GC–MS analysis, add an appropriate volume of DCM and a suitable amount of recovery determination standard (RDS) to fractions 1, 2, and 3. The volume of DCM should be selected according to the sensitivity of the GC–MS system and the expected concentrations of the target analytes in the sample fractions; however, a final volume of 50 μ L is generally recommended. The recommended amount of RDS is 20 ng, with PCB congener #157 suggested as the default standard.

6.7. Diazomethane production and addition to fraction 5

- 1 – Diazald® ethyl ether (2,14 g de Diazald in 30 ml of ethyl ether)
- 2 – Ethyl ether + Methanol (9:1)
- 3 – Ethyl ether
- 4 – Acetic acid

Figure 3. Reagents and solvents used for diazomethane generation and methylation of fraction 5

6.7.1. Add alcoholic KOH solution (0.4 g of KOH in 10 ml ethanol 96%) to the first test tube to initialize the diazo production (Figure 3). Set test tube 2 in a cup with a mix of ice+salt ($T < -10^{\circ}\text{C}$).

6.7.2. Open the nitrogen flow.

The diazomethane production is verified when the colour of test tube two change to yellow. Tube 2 will be saturated when the yellow colour is observed also in tube 3. At this moment, close the nitrogen flow and the process is finished. Tube 4 is used to neutralise the excess of diazomethane if this is produced.

6.7.3. Fill vials of fraction 5 and Total Organic Extract – DCM fraction with the test tube 2 solution.

Screw the vials and observe if the extract fractions became yellowish. If not, dry the extract and add diazomethane (test tube 2 solution) until it stays yellow.

Leave the vials to dry in a semi-opened hood during the night.

6.8. Derivatisation of F4 and F5

6.8.1. Add 100 µl of BSTFA-TMCS (N,O-bis (trimethylsilyl) trifluoroacetamide with 1% of TMCS) to vials with fractions 4 and 5.

6.8.2. Capsulate the vials and heat on a heater plate at 70°C for 1 hour. After that, set the vials to cool in a desiccator.

Note: The derivatisation procedure should be done shortly before the GC-MS analysis.

6.9. GC-MS analysis

6.9.1. Add internal standard to the vial containing the sample to be analysed.

Acknowledgments

This protocol was created in the frame of the SAPPHERE project (Source Apportionment of Airborne Particulate Matter and Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons in Urban Regions of Europe), coordinated at the University of Aveiro by Prof. Casimiro Pio, with substantial contributions from César Oliveira and Tiago Oliveira.